

Measuring Energy Efficiency Of Architectural Complexity in Modern PHP Frameworks

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Abstract

Energy consumption is a critical pillar of sustainable computing, yet the impact of software architectural complexity in web context remains under-researched. This study examines the relationship between software structure and power draw across six popular PHP frameworks. The Accidental Complexity Score (ACS), a metric quantifying a framework's structural overhead in classes, interfaces, traits, and functions, is used to correlate architectural complexity with energy consumption measured via Intel RAPL telemetry on power-optimized hardware.

The results reveal a direct correlation: frameworks with higher ACS consistently demand more power, regardless of workload intensity. This empirical evidence demonstrates that architectural minimalism is a prerequisite for energy efficiency and sustainable computing. The study concludes with a corollary to Wirth's Law, suggesting that software design choices can negate hardware-level sustainability gains.

Introduction

In recent years, the environmental impact of computing has become an increasingly critical concern. While advancements in hardware have improved performance-per-watt (Vestias and Neto, 2014) (Leech and Kazmierski, 2014), the energy consumed by software continues to rise, often negating potential hardware gains. Traditional studies of energy efficiency in computing have primarily focused on programming languages or algorithmic efficiency, providing valuable insights into execution time, memory usage, and their correlation with energy consumption (Pereira et al., 2017), (Pereira et al., 2021). However, the role of software architectural complexity in the web context remains largely unexplored, particularly regarding the overhead introduced by modern high-level frameworks.

The concept of accidental complexity suggests that structural overhead beyond an application's functional requirements can lead to measurable inefficiencies. This study extends previous investigations into modern PHP frameworks by examining their energy footprints. Six popular frameworks are analysed: Laravel, Symfony, Laminas, CodeIgniter 4, Yii, and Fat-Free.

Using Intel's Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) telemetry on power-optimized hardware (Intel Core i3-6100T), we isolate the energy footprint attributable to framework architecture. By correlating the Accidental Complexity Score (ACS), a quantitative metric that sums the number of

object-oriented and procedural components instantiated by a framework, with measured power consumption, this research provides empirical evidence linking architectural choices to physical electrical draw. The findings suggest that software design is not merely an abstract consideration but a decision with tangible environmental and operational consequences.

Literature Review

The two papers about energy efficiency across programming languages (Pereira et al., 2017), (Pereira et al., 2021) are probably the most relevant papers about energy efficiency. The first article presents an analysis about the energy efficiency of 27 well-known software languages using The Computer Language Benchmarks Game (CLBG), a free software where well-known algorithms have been implemented in various popular programming languages. Authors measured the execution time and memory usage relating them to energy in order to understand relation between memory usage and time with energy consumption. An interesting conclusion is that the faster language is not always the most energy efficient (Figure 1).

Table 4: Normalized global results for Energy, Time, and Memory

Total					
	Energy (J)		Time (ms)		Mb
(c) C	1.00	(c) C	1.00	(c) Pascal	1.00
(c) Rust	1.03	(c) Rust	1.04	(c) Go	1.05
(c) C++	1.34	(c) C++	1.56	(c) C	1.17
(c) Ada	1.70	(c) Ada	1.85	(c) Fortran	1.24
(v) Java	1.98	(v) Java	1.89	(c) C++	1.34
(c) Pascal	2.14	(c) Chapel	2.14	(c) Ada	1.47
(c) Chapel	2.18	(c) Go	2.83	(c) Rust	1.54
(v) Lisp	2.27	(c) Pascal	3.02	(v) Lisp	1.92
(c) Ocaml	2.40	(c) Ocaml	3.09	(c) Haskell	2.45
(c) Fortran	2.52	(v) C#	3.14	(i) PHP	2.57
(c) Swift	2.79	(v) Lisp	3.40	(c) Swift	2.71
(c) Haskell	3.10	(c) Haskell	3.55	(i) Python	2.80
(v) C#	3.14	(c) Swift	4.20	(c) Ocaml	2.82
(c) Go	3.23	(c) Fortran	4.20	(v) C#	2.85
(i) Dart	3.83	(v) F#	6.30	(i) Hack	3.34
(v) F#	4.13	(i) JavaScript	6.52	(v) Racket	3.52
(i) JavaScript	4.45	(i) Dart	6.67	(i) Ruby	3.97
(v) Racket	7.91	(v) Racket	11.27	(c) Chapel	4.00
(i) TypeScript	21.50	(i) Hack	26.99	(v) F#	4.25
(i) Hack	24.02	(i) PHP	27.64	(i) JavaScript	4.59
(i) PHP	29.30	(v) Erlang	36.71	(i) TypeScript	4.69
(v) Erlang	42.23	(i) Jruby	43.44	(v) Java	6.01
(i) Lua	45.98	(i) TypeScript	46.20	(i) Perl	6.62
(i) Jruby	46.54	(i) Ruby	59.34	(i) Lua	6.72
(i) Ruby	69.91	(i) Perl	65.79	(v) Erlang	7.20
(i) Python	75.88	(i) Python	71.90	(i) Dart	8.64
(i) Perl	79.58	(i) Lua	82.91	(i) Jruby	19.84

Figure 1: Normalized global results for Energy, Time, and Memory. Source: Pereira, et al. (2021)

However, Mytton (2022) argue that at the question which languages are the fastest and most efficient, the accurate answer is: it depends. The author expands this debate by arguing that energy efficiency "depends" heavily on modern hardware shifts. He highlights the rise of ARM architecture and heterogeneous computing, where "Intelligent OS" schedulers distribute tasks between Performance (P-cores) and Efficiency (E-cores). Mytton's perspective suggests that a language's raw efficiency score is only one part of a larger system where the OS manages energy based on workload characteristics.

Yet, even with an intelligent OS and an efficient base language, a third layer could exists: the accidental complexity of the software architecture. As explored in my previous paper (Davanzo, 2025b), the Accidental Complexity Score (ACS) measured in six popular PHP frameworks, shows a clear correlation between structural overhead and resources consumption.

Framework	Declared Classes	Declared Interfaces	Declared Traits	Defined Functions	ACS
Laravel	226	70	79	167	542
Symfony	135	59	11	68	273
Laminas	145	48	5	3	201
CodeIgniter 4	84	14	6	70	174
Yii Framework	40	5	0	10	55
Fat-Free Framework	11	0	0	2	13

Table 1: Accidental Complexity Score (ACS) for each framework. Source (Davanzo, 2025b)

Frameworks with higher ACS values consume significantly more memory and execution time than lightweight frameworks. So, it should be reasonable to suppose that energy efficiency could be affected. Multiple studies provide strong support for the influence of software complexity on energy consumption. (Georgiou, Rizou, and Spinellis 2019) (Capra, Francalanci and Slaughter, 2012) (Eder, 2013). Furthermore, Manotas, Pollock and Clause, (2014) shown that it is possible to improve the energy usage of an application by making code-level changes even with an automated support.

Methodology

To investigate the energy impact of accidental complexity in PHP frameworks, this study utilises a controlled experimental environment designed to isolate the software's energy footprint from background noise and hardware variability. The experiment was conducted using a dual-server setup in order to ensure that the energy consumed by the Test Runner does not interfere with the

energy measurements of the Web Server. In this occasion two Dell Optiplex 3040 units, named Edsger and Niklaus, connected via TP-Link LS1005G 5-Port Gigabit Ethernet Switch have been used (Figure 2 and Figure 3).

Figure 3: Test servers

Both servers are equipped with CPU Intel Core i3-6100T @3.20GHz, 12GB RAM and 128GB SSD with Alpine Linux v3.23, The latter is a lightweight distribution built on the musl C library and BusyBox utilities. This permits to obtain a reduced system footprint which minimizes noise in the RAPL readings.

```
edsger:~# rc-status
Runlevel: default
  crond           [ started ]
  ntpd            [ started ]
  acpid           [ started ]
  sshd            [ started ]
Dynamic Runlevel: hotplugged
Dynamic Runlevel: needed/wanted
  sysfs           [ started ]
  fsck            [ started ]
  root            [ started ]
  localmount      [ started ]
Dynamic Runlevel: manual
```

Figure 4: State of system services on Edsger

This design choice directly supports the methodological goal of isolating the energy consumption attributable to architectural complexity of the PHP frameworks under test. It should be noted that the "T" suffix on CPU type name stands for "Power-optimized lifestyle". This strengthens the research because testing for energy efficiency is performed on a CPU that was specifically designed by Intel to be energy efficient.

The server "Edsger" acts as the primary Web Server. Running nginx/1.28.0 and PHP 8.3.29, it hosts the PHP frameworks under test. The server "Niklaus" acts as the Test Runner sending HTTP requests to Edsger using an ad-hoc testing suite.

The Intel RAPL (Running Average Power Limit)

The primary tool for energy measurement in this study is the Intel Running Average Power Limit (RAPL). Introduced in the Sandy Bridge architecture, RAPL is a set of hardware counters that provide energy consumption data with high precision and low overhead. It allows the measurement of specific domains like the entire CPU package (PKG), the integrated graphics (PP1), and the DRAM by providing energy readings in micro-Joules. These readings are stored in the Model Specific Registers (MSRs), so by reading these registers during the framework's execution cycle, it is possible to calculate the total energy consumed by the software executed.

CPU turbo and governor features

To ensure the reproducibility of the results and to isolate the energy impact of architectural complexity, I implemented strict controls over the CPU's dynamic frequency scaling behaviours. Specifically, I disabled Intel Turbo Boost and setup the CPU governor to "performance".

Intel Turbo Boost is a feature that allows the processor to run faster than its rated base frequency (3.20 GHz for the i3-6100T) when there is thermal and power headroom. While beneficial for general user experience, Turbo Boost introduces non-determinism in energy measurements because changes on frequency could unpredictably happen in the middle of a test.

Modern Linux systems employ a CPU frequency governor as part of the Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS) mechanism. The governor is a kernel-level policy that determines how and when the CPU frequency should change in response to system load, thermal constraints, and power limits. Common governors include *powersave*, *ondemand*, *schedutil*, and *performance*. It is important to clarify that the performance governor does not constitute an absolute frequency lock. While it prevents opportunistic downscaling under low load, the operating system and firmware retain authority to reduce core frequencies under specific conditions. Consequently, brief frequency reductions may still be observed at the per-core level, even when the governor is set to performance and Turbo Boost is disabled.

The adtool shell scripts

To bridge the gap between the raw hardware telemetry and the experimental dataset, I used three shell scripts.

- `noturbo.sh`: A script for disabling the Intel Turbo Boost
- `performance.sh`: A utility to quickly set the scaling governor for all CPU cores to *performance* mode
- `raplog.sh`: A robust Intel RAPL (Running Average Power Limit) logger. The logic of `raplog()` is designed to account for the specific behaviour of Intel RAPL counters, which

function as cumulative energy odometers. The script implements the following technical features:

- *Metric Derivation (Cumulative to Delta)*: Because RAPL MSR values continuously increment their values in micro-joules (μJ), the script maintains the state of the previous reading in memory to calculate the Energy Delta ($\Delta\mu\text{J}$) for each specific interval.
- *Power Conversion (Wattage)*: To provide a real-time perspective on power intensity, the script automatically calculates the average Power (W) for each domain by dividing the energy delta by the measurement interval ($P=\Delta t/\Delta E$), outputting results with 9-decimal precision.
- *Automatic Domain Discovery*: The script dynamically identifies all available RAPL domains e.g., package-0, uncore, dram. This prevents hardcoding errors making it reusable in different tests.
- *System Context Logging*: Beyond energy, the script captures a synchronized snapshot of the hardware state, including:
 - *Per-core Frequencies*: Clock speeds in MHz across all logical cores.
 - *Control State*: The current CPU governor and the binary status of Intel Turbo Boost (on/off).
 - *Thermal Data*: Package temperature in degrees Celsius.
 - *Process Attribution*: A snapshot of the top active process to check if external programs like system updates interfered with the test.
 - *Orchestration Tagging*: The application supports an external `-t [tag]` flag. This allows the Test Orchestrator to inject metadata directly into the CSV rows, labeling data segments by framework name (e.g., laravel, symfony) or test phase (e.g., baseline, stress).

Test Runner Orchestration Scripts (Overview)

All experiments are orchestrated from the Test Runner machine (Nicklaus) to guarantee a separation between workload generation and energy measurement. The sole responsibility of the Test Runner is to coordinate test execution, generate HTTP traffic, and collect the data. Two shell scripts are used: a single-run orchestrator `test_frameworks.sh` and a batch runner `run_all.sh`.

The first coordinates one complete experimental run and follows a fixed sequence:

- *Remote Hardware Preparation*: Before each test, the Test Runner remotely enforces a stable hardware state on the Web Server by disabling Intel Turbo Boost, setting the CPU governor to *performance*. This ensures that all measurements start from a known and reproducible configuration.

- *Baseline Idle Measurement:* An initial idle phase is recorded with no incoming HTTP requests. During this phase, the RAPL logger runs on the Web Server and is tagged as "baseline". This establishes the static power cost of the system and provides a reference point for later comparisons.
- *Framework Execution Phase:* Each PHP framework is tested sequentially. For every framework:
 - The web stack is restarted to reset runtime state.
 - Energy logging is started and tagged with the framework name.
 - The Test Runner generates HTTP requests for a fixed duration at controlled rates.
- *Data Collection:* At the end of the run, the consolidated RAPL log is retrieved from the Web Server and stored alongside the local logical record of every HTTP request made (event log).

The second script automates repeated executions of the single-run test:

- Each delay configuration is executed multiple times to reduce noise.
- A sleep period is enforced between runs.
- Baseline power levels are checked to detect anomalous runs.

The baseline and each framework have been tested three times for 300 seconds per test and five inter-request delays are used to explore different workload intensities: 0.010, 0.050, 0.100, 0.200, and 1.000 seconds .

Inter-request Delay (s)	Requests per Second (RPS)	Workload scenario
0.010	100.0	Very high
0.050	20.0	High
0.100	10.0	Moderate
0.200	5.0	Low
1.000	1.0	Sparse

Table 2: Inter-request delay and scenario definitions

It is important to note that the workload scenarios reported in Table 2 are relative classifications used exclusively within the context of this study. The labels Very high, High, Moderate, Low, and Sparse refer to the comparative request pressure applied during the controlled experiments, not to

absolute real-world traffic limits. In production environments, real-world web applications may sustain request rates that are orders of magnitude higher than those explored here. The selected request-per-second values are intentionally constrained to maintain experimental stability, avoid server saturation, and ensure that observed energy differences remain attributable to framework architectural complexity rather than to uncontrolled overload conditions.

Frameworks setup

The experimental environment utilises the same six PHP frameworks and directory structures established in previous Audax Development Research Notes 1 (Davanzo, 2025a). This maintains the Accidental Complexity Score (ACS) as a consistent independent variable. The only change to the original setup has been the removal of calling the `cesp_log()` function for two reasons: the first is to eliminate the computational and I/O overhead caused by processing and logging. The second is to ensure Intel RAPL readings reflect only the framework's native architectural cost and the "Hello World" execution.

Results

This section presents the aggregated power consumption results obtained from the controlled experiments described in the previous sections (Table 3 to Table 7, Figure 5 to Figure 9). For each workload configuration, power values are reported as minimum, average, and maximum wattage measured at the CPU package level (RAPL:0), grouped by framework and compared against an idle baseline. The complete results for each individual test run are provided in the Appendix.

Baseline Stability

Across all test configurations, the baseline measurements remain remarkably stable. The average baseline power consumption consistently ranges between 2.84 W and 2.85 W, with minimal variation in minimum and maximum values. This stability confirms that the experimental environment is well controlled and that observed power differences during framework execution are attributable to application activity rather than background system noise.

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	798	2.417657	2.846413	3.089836
fat-free	801	3.411368	3.764754	4.012441
yii	801	3.575675	3.808968	4.299183
symfony	801	3.705801	3.945235	6.404952
laminas	801	3.826833	4.053807	4.4287
ci4	800	3.931996	4.203545	4.524707
laravel	801	4.555347	4.950947	6.919355

Table 3: Tests summary with inter-delay 0.010s

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	798	2.446039	2.848495	3.047538
fat-free	801	2.903679	3.190981	3.399039
yii	801	3.049614	3.208786	3.537344
symfony	801	3.151115	3.272517	3.511283
laminas	801	3.200798	3.314785	3.533256
ci4	801	3.27996	3.392398	3.603995
laravel	801	3.600821	3.960111	6.940107

Table 4: Test summary with inter-delay 0.050s

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	798	2.40777	2.848731	3.055229
fat-free	801	2.820672	3.048041	3.250114
yii	801	2.88195	3.059839	3.283439
symfony	801	3.003533	3.090851	3.423698
laminas	801	3.044487	3.122813	3.343559
ci4	801	3.056267	3.170757	3.372123
laravel	801	3.256705	3.459523	6.582869

Table 5: Test summary with inter-delay 0.100s

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	798	2.42785	2.848139	3.059867
fat-free	801	2.697381	2.958069	3.196708
yii	801	2.76397	2.966135	3.167106
symfony	801	2.914544	2.98844	3.179862
laminas	801	2.929008	2.998107	3.200797
ci4	801	2.954949	3.029028	3.258964
laravel	801	3.064995	3.178731	4.788745

Table 6: Test summary with inter-delay 0.200s

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	798	2.429804	2.847344	3.058037
fat-free	801	2.490717	2.874423	3.087883
yii	801	2.59887	2.874704	3.077934
symfony	802	2.80938	2.882816	3.089591
laminas	803	2.814385	2.886425	3.097343
ci4	802	2.733575	2.889517	3.10839
laravel	801	2.844597	2.927437	4.058034

Table 7: Test summary with inter-delay 1.000s

Figure 5: Summary of intel-rapl:0 average (W) with inter-delay 0.010s

Figure 6: Summary of intel-rapl:0 average (W) with inter-delay 0.050s

Figure 7: Summary of intel-rapl:0 average (W) with inter-delay 0.100s

Figure 8: Summary of intel-rapl:0 average (W) with inter-delay 0.200s

Figure 9: Summary of intel-rapl:0 average (W) with inter-delay 1.000s

Impact of Request Rate on Power Consumption

The relationship between request frequency and power consumption reveals the dynamic cost of architectural abstractions. The power delta $\Delta P = AVG_{framework} - AVG_{baseline}$ serves as a direct proxy for the energy efficiency of a framework's internal structure. As shown in Table 8, the data demonstrates shows a clear relationship between request rate and average power consumption across all frameworks. As the inter-request delay decreases i.e., higher requests per second, average power consumption increases, which is something expected. At the highest load condition (0.010 s

delay, ~100 RPS), average power consumption spans from 3.764754 W (Fat-Free) to 4.950947 W (Laravel), whereas at the lowest load condition (1.000 s delay, 1 RPS) average values spans from 2.874423 W (Fat-Free) to 2.927437 W (Laravel).

Moreover, even at the lowest load (1.000s), the measurements confirm that while the difference appears small, specifically 2.927437 W for Laravel vs. 2.847344 W for the idle Baseline, the resulting 0.08 W delta is attributable to accidental complexity. When scaled to thousands of servers, this represents a continuous power draw resulting from the framework's structural requirements rather than application logic. On the other side, this is more visible when the data are expressed as percentage increase relative to the baseline calculated as:

$$\text{Percentage Increase} = \left(\frac{\text{Framework AVG} - \text{Baseline AVG}}{\text{Baseline AVG}} \right) \times 100$$

Framework	0.010s	0.050s	0.100s	0.200s	1.000s
Fat-Free	0.918341 (32.25%)	0.342486 (12.02%)	0.19931 (7.00%)	0.10993 (3.86%)	0.027079 (0.95%)
Yii	0.962555 (33.82%)	0.360291 (12.65%)	0.211108 (7.41%)	0.117996 (4.14%)	0.027360 (0.96%)
Symfony	1.098822 (38.60%)	0.424022 (14.89%)	0.24212 (8.50%)	0.140301 (4.93%)	0.035472 (1.25%)
Laminas	1.207394 (42.42%)	0.46629 (16.37%)	0.274082 (9.62%)	0.149968 (5.27%)	0.039081 (1.37%)
CI4	1.357132 (47.68%)	0.543903 (19.09%)	0.322026 (11.30%)	0.180889 (6.35%)	0.042173 (1.48%)
Laravel	2.104534 (73.94%)	1.111616 (39.02%)	0.610792 (21.44%)	0.330592 (11.61%)	0.080093 (2.81%)

Table 8: Power delta and percentage increase in consumption for each framework relative to the baseline

Framework-Specific Power Profiles

Despite identical workloads, frameworks exhibit consistent and distinguishable power profiles across all load levels:

- *Fat-Free* consistently demonstrates the lowest average power consumption among the tested frameworks.
- *Yii* and *Symfony* occupy an intermediate position, with closely clustered average values.

- *Laminas* and *CodeIgniter 4* exhibit moderately higher power consumption.
- *Laravel* consistently records the highest average and maximum power consumption at every request rate.

These relative positions remain stable across all tested delays, suggesting that the observed differences are structural rather than incidental.

Correlation with Accidental Complexity Score (ACS)

The experimental data reveals a relationship between a framework's structural volume and its dynamic power consumption across the test tiers.

Framework	ACS (from Table 1)	AVG Power @ 0.010s
Fat-Free	13	3.76 W
Yii	55	3.80 W
CodeIgniter 4	174	4.20 W
Laminas	201	4.05 W
Symfony	273	3.94 W
Laravel	542	4.95 W

Table 9: Correlation between ACS and average power

This suggests that the Accidental Complexity Score (ACS) serves as a meaningful indicator of energy efficiency, establishing a clear link between a framework's structural density and its electrical draw. While the mid-tier results (notably Symfony and Laminas) suggest that specific implementation efficiencies also influence wattage, the overall trend remains evident: the architectural extremes represented by the minimalist Fat-Free (13 ACS) and the complex Laravel (542 ACS), consistently define the lower and upper bounds of power consumption.

Conclusions

This research provides empirical evidence that the internal architecture of a software framework in the web context, is a primary determinant of its electrical footprint. By utilizing Intel RAPL telemetry on power-optimized hardware, the study demonstrates that energy consumption is not merely a product of the workload, but is fundamentally governed by the structural overhead of the framework itself. Hence, the experimental data reveal that energy efficiency is inversely proportional to architectural complexity.

These findings reveal that architectural complexity acts as a structural energy leakage, causing a continuous environmental drain that persists independently of the application's actual utility. While a sub-watt difference between frameworks may seem negligible for a single request, it represents a persistent baseline of energy waste. This overhead cannot be reclaimed by hardware-level power

management. In the context of hyperscale cloud environments, where thousands of servers and containers execute these frameworks simultaneously, this structural burden scales into a significant and avoidable electrical load.

Ultimately, this study demonstrates that energy efficiency is a first-class architectural attribute. These results lead to the formulation of my personal corollary to Wirth's Law:

"Software increases its energy demand more rapidly than hardware improves its power efficiency."

Even when deployed on hardware specifically designed for efficiency, the software's internal complexity dictates the final energy outcome. For organizations aiming to meet sustainability goals, these results suggest that framework selection should be treated as a strategic energy-management decision. Consequently, the choice of a high-ACS framework represents a measurable, long-term environmental footprint. Therefore, architectural minimalism is not just a design philosophy or preference; it is a prerequisite for energy-efficient and environmentally friendly software engineering.

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Appendix

Tests results with inter-delay 0.010s

Test 1

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.432611	2.848196	3.054253
ci4	267	3.989736	4.218887	4.523976
fat-free	267	3.411368	3.755067	3.983571
laminas	267	3.826833	4.053277	4.358509
laravel	267	4.555347	4.776946	5.7025
symfony	267	3.728323	3.953328	6.404952
yii	267	3.609549	3.818185	4.145803

Test 2

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.417657	2.846661	3.033744
ci4	267	3.931996	4.199732	4.524707
fat-free	267	3.584952	3.77582	4.008596
laminas	267	3.883108	4.057715	4.4287
laravel	267	4.560291	4.964257	6.353011
symfony	267	3.711905	3.953004	4.224904
yii	267	3.58483	3.799584	4.13152

Test 3

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.489618	2.844383	3.089836
ci4	266	3.982595	4.191973	4.519764
fat-free	267	3.535452	3.763376	4.012441
laminas	267	3.858084	4.050429	4.295521
laravel	267	4.577991	5.111636	6.919355
symfony	267	3.705801	3.929372	4.244985
yii	267	3.575675	3.809135	4.299183

Tests results with inter-delay 0.050s

Test 1

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.446039	2.852822	3.035271
ci4	267	3.293326	3.394953	3.59191
fat-free	267	2.960015	3.192392	3.388236
laminas	267	3.200798	3.309819	3.499319
laravel	267	3.626699	3.992505	6.867781
symfony	267	3.160209	3.275719	3.464102
yii	267	3.069328	3.216442	3.537344

Test 2

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.476739	2.849623	3.047538
ci4	267	3.288138	3.385426	3.571829
fat-free	267	2.944999	3.193727	3.399039
laminas	267	3.231315	3.316081	3.51763
laravel	267	3.610159	3.95594	6.940107
symfony	267	3.151115	3.274093	3.511283
yii	267	3.049614	3.208635	3.399832

Test 3

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.450006	2.843038	3.024834
ci4	267	3.27996	3.396816	3.603995
fat-free	267	2.903679	3.186824	3.389762
laminas	267	3.220451	3.318456	3.533256
laravel	267	3.600821	3.931888	6.544478
symfony	267	3.17028	3.26774	3.469657
yii	267	3.081901	3.201282	3.40734

Tests results with inter-delay 0.100s

Test 1

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.459771	2.848894	3.055229
ci4	267	3.056267	3.170685	3.34722
fat-free	267	2.844597	3.047521	3.229362
laminas	267	3.048271	3.125489	3.343559
laravel	267	3.271476	3.473489	6.582869
symfony	267	3.003533	3.091644	3.309074
yii	267	2.910332	3.056159	3.277031

Test 2

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.40777	2.850551	3.039482
ci4	267	3.101737	3.172017	3.355216
fat-free	267	2.822381	3.05084	3.250114
laminas	267	3.044487	3.123653	3.324394
laravel	267	3.256705	3.450951	5.550645
symfony	267	3.01635	3.089984	3.320731
yii	267	2.88195	3.064681	3.24224

Test 3

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.441216	2.846747	3.039054
ci4	267	3.081291	3.169568	3.372123
fat-free	267	2.820672	3.045761	3.244193
laminas	267	3.053764	3.119297	3.305107
laravel	267	3.266898	3.45413	4.941211
symfony	267	3.017204	3.090924	3.423698
yii	267	2.900261	3.058676	3.283439

Tests results with inter-delay 0.200s

Test 1

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.42785	2.848265	3.01281
ci4	267	2.960869	3.028676	3.258964
fat-free	267	2.697381	2.958705	3.183403
laminas	267	2.936272	2.993431	3.172294
laravel	267	3.078483	3.175916	4.788745
symfony	267	2.918999	2.986779	3.169059
yii	267	2.792473	2.96322	3.150016

Test 2

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.43255	2.845133	3.049248
ci4	267	2.954949	3.027184	3.209831
fat-free	267	2.704156	2.96029	3.196708
laminas	267	2.929008	3.002021	3.180717
laravel	267	3.064995	3.185659	4.244312
symfony	267	2.914544	2.985909	3.161003
yii	267	2.827813	2.968596	3.167106

Test 3

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.4508	2.851018	3.059867
ci4	267	2.960015	3.031223	3.23571
fat-free	267	2.896111	2.955211	3.143913
laminas	267	2.930656	2.998869	3.200797
laravel	267	3.076286	3.174617	4.237538
symfony	267	2.927299	2.992633	3.179862
yii	267	2.76397	2.966589	3.164787

Tests results with inter-delay 1.000s

Test 1

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.429804	2.846598	3.058037
ci4	268	2.799004	2.892039	3.101127
fat-free	267	2.507012	2.87207	3.087883
laminas	267	2.819268	2.88651	3.079155
laravel	267	2.849114	2.926978	4.058034
symfony	268	2.817314	2.881662	3.089591
yii	267	2.651238	2.873832	3.077934

Test 2

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.435358	2.847271	3.049247
ci4	267	2.733575	2.887142	3.079033
fat-free	267	2.516473	2.875982	3.084953
laminas	268	2.822076	2.885184	3.075431
laravel	267	2.85064	2.928926	3.628348
symfony	267	2.80938	2.884787	3.081779
yii	267	2.65844	2.872306	3.060051

Test 3

TAG	#	MIN	AVG	MAX
baseline	266	2.468866	2.848162	3.054801
ci4	267	2.791741	2.889362	3.10839
fat-free	267	2.490717	2.875216	3.060783
laminas	268	2.814385	2.88758	3.097343
laravel	267	2.844597	2.926407	3.563956
symfony	267	2.825005	2.882004	3.045586
yii	267	2.59887	2.877973	3.072196

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Software And Data Availability

The complete source code, automation scripts, and raw log files used in this project are openly available and permanently archived at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18278789>

AI Usage Statement

This research made limited use of an AI language model to assist in drafting baseline scripts. The AI did not make autonomous decisions, and all outputs were critically reviewed, edited, and approved by the author prior to use.